

On the Smarandache reciprocal function and its mean value

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Abstract For any positive integer n , the Smarandache reciprocal function $S_c(n)$ is defined as the largest positive integer m such that $y \mid n!$ for all integers $1 \leq y \leq m$, and $m + 1 \nmid n!$. The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary and analytic methods to study the mean value distribution properties of $S_c(n)$, and give two interesting mean value formulas for it.

Keywords The Smarandache reciprocal function, mean value, asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction and result

For any positive integer n , the famous Smarandache function $S(n)$ is defined as the smallest positive integer m such that $n \mid m!$. That is, $S(n) = \min\{m : n \mid m!, n \in N\}$. And the Smarandache reciprocal function $S_c(n)$ is defined as the largest positive integer m such that $y \mid n!$ for all integers $1 \leq y \leq m$, and $m + 1 \nmid n!$. That is, $S_c(n) = \max\{m : y \mid n! \text{ for all } 1 \leq y \leq m, \text{ and } m + 1 \nmid n!\}$. The first few values of $S_c(n)$ are:

$$\begin{aligned} S_c(1) &= 1, S_c(2) = 2, S_c(3) = 3, S_c(4) = 4, S_c(5) = 6, S_c(6) = 6, \\ S_c(7) &= 10, S_c(8) = 10, S_c(9) = 10, S_c(10) = 10, S_c(11) = 12, S_c(12) = 12, \\ S_c(13) &= 16, S_c(14) = 16, S_c(15) = 16, S_c(16) = 16, S_c(17) = 18, \dots \end{aligned}$$

About the properties of $S(n)$, many authors had studied it, and obtained a series results, see references [1], [2], [3], [4], [5] and [15]. For example, Jozsef Sandor [4] proved that for any positive integer $k \geq 2$, there exist infinite group positive integers (m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k) satisfied the following inequality:

$$S(m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_k) > S(m_1) + S(m_2) + \dots + S(m_k).$$

Also, there exist infinite group positive integers (m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k) such that

$$S(m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_k) < S(m_1) + S(m_2) + \dots + S(m_k).$$

On the other hand, in reference [6], A.Murthy studied the elementary properties of $S_c(n)$, and proved the following conclusion:

If $S_c(n) = x$ and $n \neq 3$, then $x + 1$ is the smallest prime greater than n .

The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary and analytic methods to study the mean value properties of the Smarandache reciprocal function $S_c(n)$, and give two interesting mean value formulas it. That is, we shall prove the following conclusions:

Theorem 1. For any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} S_c(n) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot x^2 + O\left(x^{\frac{19}{12}}\right).$$

Theorem 2. For any real number $x > 1$, we have the low bound estimate

$$\frac{1}{x} \sum_{n \leq x} (S_c(n) - n)^2 \geq \frac{1}{3} \cdot \ln^2 x + O\left(x^{-\frac{5}{12}} \cdot \ln^2 x\right).$$

From Theorem 2 we may immediately deduce the following:

Corollary. The limit

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{x} \sum_{n \leq x} (S_c(n) - n)^2$$

does not exist.

§2. Proof of the theorems

In this section, we shall prove our theorems directly. First we prove Theorem 1. For any real number $x > 1$, let $2 = p_1 < p_2 < \dots < p_k \leq x$ denote all primes less than or equal to x . Then from the result of A.Murthy [6] we have the identity

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} S_c(n) &= S_c(1) + S_c(2) + S_c(3) + S_c(4) + \sum_{i=3}^{k-1} \sum_{p_i \leq n < p_{i+1}} S_c(n) + \sum_{p_k \leq n \leq x} S_c(n) \\ &= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + \sum_{i=3}^{k-1} \sum_{p_i \leq n < p_{i+1}} (p_{i+1} - 1) + \sum_{p_k \leq n \leq x} (p_{k+1} - 1) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} (p_{i+1} - p_i)(p_{i+1} - 1) + O((x - p_k)(p_{k+1} - 1)) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} [(p_{i+1} - p_i)^2 + p_{i+1}^2 - p_i^2] - \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} (p_{i+1} - p_i) + O((x - p_k) \cdot p_{k+1}) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} (p_{i+1} - p_i)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot p_k^2 - p_k + O((x - p_k) \cdot p_{k+1}). \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

For any real number x large enough, from M.N.Huxley [7] we know that there at least exists a prime in the interval $\left[x, x + x^{\frac{7}{12}}\right]$. So we have the estimate

$$(x - p_k) \cdot p_{k+1} = O\left(x^{\frac{19}{12}}\right). \tag{2}$$

On the other hand, from the D.R.Heath-Brown’s famous result [8], [9] and [10] we know that for any real number $\epsilon > 0$, we have the estimate

$$\sum_{i=1}^{k-1} (p_{i+1} - p_i)^2 \ll x^{\frac{23}{18} + \epsilon}. \tag{3}$$

Note that $p_k = x + O\left(x^{\frac{7}{12}}\right)$, from (1), (2) and (3) we may immediately get the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} S_c(n) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left[x + O\left(x^{\frac{7}{12}}\right) \right]^2 + O\left(x^{\frac{19}{12}}\right) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot x^2 + O\left(x^{\frac{19}{12}}\right).$$

This proves Theorem 1.

Now we prove Theorem 2. For any real number $x > 1$, from the definition and properties of $S_c(n)$ we also have the identity

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} (S_c(n) - n)^2 &\geq \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{p_i \leq n < p_{i+1}} (S_c(n) - n)^2 = \sum_{i=3}^{k-1} \sum_{0 \leq n < p_{i+1} - p_i} (p_{i+1} - p_i - n - 1)^2 \\ &= \sum_{i=3}^{k-1} \sum_{0 \leq n < p_{i+1} - p_i} \left[(p_{i+1} - p_i)^2 - 2(n + 1) \cdot (p_{i+1} - p_i) + (n + 1)^2 \right] \\ &= \sum_{i=3}^{k-1} \left[(p_{i+1} - p_i)^3 - (p_{i+1} - p_i)^2 \cdot (p_{i+1} - p_i + 1) \right] + \\ &\quad + \sum_{i=3}^{k-1} \left[\frac{1}{6} \cdot (p_{i+1} - p_i + 1) \cdot (p_{i+1} - p_i) \cdot (2p_{i+1} - 2p_i + 1) \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=3}^{k-1} (p_{i+1} - p_i)^3 - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=3}^{k-1} (p_{i+1} - p_i)^2 + \frac{1}{6} \sum_{i=3}^{k-1} (p_{i+1} - p_i) \\ &= \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=3}^{k-1} (p_{i+1} - p_i)^3 - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=3}^{k-1} (p_{i+1} - p_i)^2 + \frac{1}{6} (p_k - p_3). \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

From the Cauchy inequality and the Prime Theorem (see references [11], [12], [13] and [14]) we may get

$$p_k - p_3 = \sum_{i=3}^{k-1} (p_{i+1} - p_i) \leq \left(\sum_{i=3}^{k-1} 1 \right)^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\sum_{i=3}^{k-1} (p_{i+1} - p_i)^3 \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} = (\pi(x) - 3)^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\sum_{i=3}^{k-1} (p_{i+1} - p_i)^3 \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}.$$

That is,

$$\left(x + O\left(x^{\frac{7}{12}}\right) \right)^3 = (p_k - p_3)^3 \leq \left(\frac{x}{\ln x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^2 x}\right) \right)^2 \cdot \left(\sum_{i=3}^{k-1} (p_{i+1} - p_i)^3 \right)$$

or

$$\sum_{i=3}^{k-1} (p_{i+1} - p_i)^3 \geq x \cdot \ln^2 x + O\left(x^{\frac{7}{12}} \cdot \ln^2 x\right). \tag{5}$$

Combining (4) and (5) we may immediately deduce the low bound estimate

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (S_c(n) - n)^2 \geq \frac{1}{3} \cdot x \cdot \ln^2 x + O\left(x^{\frac{7}{12}} \cdot \ln^2 x\right).$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 2.

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